

ISic3439

I.Sicily inscription 3439

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

Mineo

Provenance

contrada S. Ippolito

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mineo, Museo Civico Corrado
Tamburino Merlini

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644918

Bibliography

Messina, A. 1992. Mineo. In Nenci, G., Vallet, G.(eds.), *Bibliografia topografica della colonizzazione greca in Italia e nelle Isole Tirreniche*. Pisa. pp. 145-151. At 146

Gentili, G.V. 1959. Resti tardo-romani e bizantini in contrada Favarotta. *Fasti Archaeologici*. 14: no. 6918.

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